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STUDY OF NATIONAL POLICY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract :

Education has always been accorded an honoured place in Indian society. The great leaders of the Indian freedom movement realized the fundamental role of education and throughout the nation's struggle for independence stressed its unique significance for national development. Gandhiji formulated the scheme of Basic Education seeking to harmonize Intellectual and manual work. This was a great step forward in making education directly relevant to the life of the people. Many other national leaders likewise made important contributions to national education before Independence.

Commission (1964-66 was appointed to advise the Government on "the national pattern of education and on the general principles and policies for the development of education at all stages and in all aspects". The Report of the Education Commission has since been widely discussed and commented upon. The government was happy to note that a general consensus on the national policy on education has emerged in the course of these discussions.

Introduction:

The Government of India is convinced that a radical reconstruction of education on the broad lines recommended by the Education Commission is essential for economic and cultural development of the country, for national integration and for realizing the ideal of a socialistic pattern of society. This will involve a transformation of the system to values. The education system most produces young men and women of character and ability committed to national service and development. Only then will education be able to play its vital role in promoting national progress, creating a sense of common citizenship and culture, and strengthening national integration. This is necessary if the country is to attain its rightful place in the comity of nations in conformity with its great cultural heritage and its unique potentialities.

The Government of India accordingly resolves to promote the development of education in the country in accordance with the following principles:

1. Free and Compulsory Education

Strenuous efforts should be made for the early fulfillment of the Directive Principle under article 45 of the Constitution seeking to provide free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14. Suitable programmes should be developed to reduce the prevailing wastage and stagnation in schools and to ensure that every child who is enrolled in school successfully completes the prescribed course.

2. Status, Emoluments and Education off Teachers

Of all factors which determine the quality of education and its contribution to national

development, the teacher is undoubtedly the most important. It is on his personal qualities and character, his educational qualifications and professional competence that the success of all educational endeavour must ultimately depend. Teachers must, therefore, be accorded an honoured place in society. Their emoluments and other service conditions should be adequate and satisfactory, having regard to their qualifications and responsibilities.

The academic freedom of teachers to pursue and publish independent studies and researches and to speak and write about significant national and international issues should be protected.

Teacher education, particularly in- service education, should receive due emphasis.

3. Development of Languages

Regional Languages: The energetic development of Indian languages and literature is a sine qua non for educational and cultural development. Unless this is done, the creative energies of the people will not be released, standards of education will not improve, knowledge will not spread to the people, and the gulf should now be taken to adopt them as media of education at the university stage.

Three Languages Formula: At the secondary stage, the State Governments should adopt, and vigorously implement, the three language formula which includes the study of a modern Indian language, preferably one of the southern languages, apart from Hindi and English in the Hindi- speaking States, and of Hindi along with the regional language and English in the non-Hindi speaking States. Suitable courses in Hindi and/ or English should also be available in universities and colleges with a view to improving the proficiency of students in these languages up to the prescribed university standards.

Hindi : Every effort should be made to promote the development of Hindi. In developing Hindi as the link language, due care should be taken to ensure that it will serve, as provided for in Article 351 of the Constitution, as a medium of expression for all the elements of the composite culture of India. The establishment, in non- Hindi States, of colleges and other institutions of higher education which use Hindi as the medium of education should be encouraged.

Sanskrit Considering the special importance of Sanskrit to the growth and development of Indian languages and its unique contribution to the cultural unity of the country, facilities for its teaching at the school and university stages should be offered on a more liberal scale. Development of new methods of teaching the language should be encouraged, and the possibility explored of including the study of Sanskrit in those courses (such as modern Indian Languages, ancient Indian history, Indology and Indian philosophy) at the first and second degree stages, where such knowledge is useful.

International Languages: Special emphasis needs to be laid on the study of English and other International languages. World knowledge is growing at a tremendous pace, especially in science and technology. India must not only keep up this growth but should also make her own significant contribution to it. For this purpose, study of English deserves to be specially strengthened.

4. Equalization of Educational Opportunity

Strenuous efforts should be made to equalize educational opportunity. Regional imbalances in the provision of educational facilities Commission School System as

The possibility of establishing autonomous book corporations on commercial lines should be examined and efforts should be made to have a few basic textbooks common throughout the country. Special attention should be given to books for children and to university level books in regional languages.

10. Examinations

A major goal of examination reforms should be to improve the reliability and validity of examinations and to make evaluation a continuous process aimed at helping the student to improve his level of achievement rather than at certifying the quality of his performance at a given moment of time.

11. Secondary Education

Educational opportunity at the secondary (and higher) level is a major instrument of social change and transformation. Facilities for secondary education should accordingly be extended expeditiously to the areas and classes which have been denied these in the past.

Vocational education should conform broadly to the requirements of the developing economy and real employment opportunities. Such linkage is necessary to make technical and vocational education at the secondary stage effectively terminal. Facilities for technical and vocational education should be suitably diversified to cover a large number of fields, such as agriculture, industry, trade and commerce, medicine and public health, home management, arts and crafts, secretarial training, etc.

12. University Education

The number of whole time students to be admitted to a college or university department should be determined with reference to the laboratory, library and other facilities and to the strength of the staff.

Considerable care is needed in establishing new universities. These should be started only after an adequate provision of funds has been made for the purpose and due care has been taken to ensure proper standards.

Special attention should be given to the organization of post graduate courses and to the improvement of standards of training and research at this level

Centers of advanced study should be strengthened and a small number of 'clusters of centers' aiming at the highest possible standards in research and training should be established.

There is a need to give increased support to research in universities generally. The institutions for research should, as far as possible, function within the fold of universities or in intimate association with them.

13. Part- time Education and Correspondence Courses

Part- time education and correspondence courses should be developed on a large scale at the university stage. Such facilities should also be developed for secondary school students, for teachers and for agricultural, industrial and other workers. Education through part- time and correspondence course should be given the same status as full- time education. Such facilities will smoothen transition from school to work, promote the cause of education and provide opportunities to the large number of people who have the desire to educate themselves further but cannot do so on a full- time basis.

Meeting participation in the working on democratic measures and for accelerating programmes of production, especially in agriculture, but for quickening the tempo of national

development in general. Employees in large commercial, industrial and other concerns should be made functionally literate as early as possible. A lead in this direction should come from the industrial undertakings in the public sector. Teachers and students should be actively involved in organizing literacy campaigns, especially as part of the Social and National Service Programme. Special emphasis should be given to the education of young practicing farmers and to the training of youth for self- employment.

15. Games and Sports

Games and sports should be developed on a large scale with the object of improving the physical fitness and sportsmanship of the average student as well as of those who excel in this department. Where playing field and other facilities for developing a nation-wide programme of physical education do not exist, these should be provided on a priority basis.

16. Education of Minorities

Every effort should be made not only to protect the rights of minorities but to promote their educational interests as suggested in the statement issued by the Conference of the Chief Ministers of States and Central Ministers held in August 1961.

17. The Educational Structure

It will be advantageous to have a broadly uniform educational structure in all parts of the country. The ultimate objective should be to adopt the 10+2+3 pattern, the higher secondary stage of two years being located in schools, colleges or both according to local conditions.

The reconstruction of education on the lines indicated above will need additional outlay. The aim should be gradually to increase the investment in education so as to reach a level of expenditure of 6 percent of the national income as early as possible.

The Government of India recognizes that reconstruction of education is no easy task. Not only are the resources scarce but the problem are exceedingly complex. Considering the key role which education science and research play in developing the material and human resources of the country, the Government of India will, in addition to ments for the development of programmes of national importance where coordinated action on the part of the States and the Centre is called for.

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